

Analysis of Bilateral Trade Flow and Machine Learning Algorithms for GDP Forecasting

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Abstract—The terms imports and exports describe goods and services traded between countries. Countries import goods they cannot produce domestically or can obtain at a lower cost from another country. According to the World Trade Organization (WTO) reports, the U.S. is the world's largest importer based on capital investment, followed by the E.U., China, Germany, and Japan. For exports, China leads the world with an official trade amount of \$1.904 trillion in 2013. E.U. ranks second, followed by U.S., Germany, and Japan. Trade in goods and services is defined as a change in ownership of material resources and services between economies. Trade indicators include the sale of goods and services as well as barter transactions or goods exchanged and are measured in million USD, the percentage of GDP for net trade, and the annual export and import growth. This study analyzes imports and exports of all countries for the 1960-2017 period and evaluates the correlations in trade statistics to predict future imports and exports. Since the GDP for any country depends mainly on trade, this study examines trade data and compares various machine learning algorithms to forecast a country's GDP.

Keywords—imports; exports; GDP; trade statistics; GDP forecast

I. INTRODUCTION

Trade data include exports, imports, and trade balance. In general, international trade represents the economic activity of a country related to some economic relationship with another country. A series of such activities forms a country's trade balance. The trade volume of a country indicates the country's collective effect of macroeconomic policies. Analyzing this effect from international trade policies requires data on the country's exports and imports and the long-run equilibrium relationship between these two variables. Here, there always is the effect of time lag on trade volume since any change in a country's import/export demand does not happen quickly, and therefore, trade data require a deep analysis [1]. One factor in explaining trade remains the comparative advantage. However, some new factors such as consumer preferences, advantages in

the economy of scale, and the use of global production have emerged, and such factors may alter international trade patterns. In addition, bilateral trade is important in understanding the consequences of international trade [2].

Economies that are oriented mainly toward trade must carefully analyze their bilateral trade data since international trade flow and its direction, composition, and linkages require bilateral as well as multilateral analyses. Therefore, data should always be carefully examined in any empirical analysis [3]. Several studies have analyzed exports, imports, the economy, and their relationships, including cointegration between exports and imports [4, 5], long-run trade elasticity in less developed countries [6], cointegration in specific groups of countries [7], and related technical issues [8]. Some studies have investigated the importance of exports and imports in forming the economy and improving the quality of life [9]. There are various methods for determining the importance of exports and imports in the economy and analyzing their impacts on economic growth. One uses simple (and sometimes multiple) regression between these three variables and other factors, and another employs causality, determining the factors and causes as well as inverse causality. Some studies have used VAR and VEC models to exclude this causality problem. A cointegration test has verified a long-run equilibrium relationship between GDP, exports, and imports in Tunisia [10], finding these two variables to influence economic growth and thus highlighting their importance. A study of the Nigerian economy has suggested economic growth to be determined by exports, imports, labor, and the exchange rate and posited their cointegration, also showing positive relationships of exports and labor to economic growth and negative effects of imports and the exchange rate on the economy [11]. A study of the Ethiopian economy has revealed that the growth rate of real exports has a positive relationship with the rate of economic growth, analyzing that, although the effect is non-significant in the short run, there is a strong long-run relationship between

these two variables [12]. These studies show that exports and imports have great impacts on economic growth. Economic growth is typically represented with GDP, GDP per capita, trade balance, consumption, investment, and government spending.

In addition to the impact on economic growth, exports and imports are important for other reasons. An example is the model of innovation and trade, which predicts positive shocks in exports can facilitate more productive and innovative firms. Here the accompanying rent from the innovation effort of companies increases with the firm's market size, known as the market size effect [13]. A country's GDP is a primary indicator of the country's economy. GDP represents the worth (in dollars) of all goods and services produced and imported/exported over a period of time. This is measured relative to previous GDP. An increase in GDP shows the growth of a country's economy, and this figure is considered a key benchmark for the country's economy. The U.S. has the largest GDP in the world, followed by China, Japan, Germany, the U.K., France, and India. In most cases GDP measurement is complicated. In simple terms, GDP is the income earned (gross profit) and expenditure spent by a country, and since it is considered relative to countries, exports and imports play a vital role in deciding a country's GDP. GDP can be calculated as the total spending on all final goods and services (Consumption of goods and services (C) + Gross Investments (I) + Government Purchases (G) + (Exports (X) - Imports (M)), i.e. $GDP=C+I+G+(X-M)$.

II. WORLD TRADE DATA STATISTICS

Trade statistics represent a unique dataset for modern economies. Trade data statistics can indicate economic geography and provide insights into economic development and globalization. International trade plays an important role in a wage-based economy. International trade data provide insights into global relationships between countries as well as information on the relationship between local and regional economies [14]. Statistical data confirm that trade has continued to support economic growth and development, helping to reduce poverty around the world. World merchandise exports have increased in value by about 32% since 2006, reaching USD 16 trillion in 2016. At the same time, world exports of commercial services have accelerated by about 64%, reaching a total of USD 4.77 trillion [15]. The importance of world trade data statistics is clear, but its usefulness depends on various factors such as data availability, analysis requirements, and data accuracy. Therefore, measuring trade statistics must adhere to the Standard International Trade Classification [16]. This is important since insufficient data or analysis may cause misinterpretation of variables. According to the World Fact book, the world's top exporter is China with the total export of \$2.157 trillion in 2017, followed by the E.U. with \$1.929 trillion in 2016 and the U.S. with \$1.576 trillion in 2017 [17]. For top import countries, the World Fact book ranks U.S. as the leader with \$2.352 trillion of total imports in 2017, followed by E.U. with \$1.895 trillion in 2016 and China with \$1.731 trillion in 2017 [18]. Germany and Japan followed. The total import for Germany was \$1.104 trillion in 2017, and Japan was \$625.7 billion in 2017. For exports, Germany

exported \$1.401 trillion in 2017, and Japan, \$683.3 in 2017 [17, 18]. The top 18 world imports and exports can be seen in [19]. Cars top the list, with Germany as the largest exporter and the U.S. as the top importer. Refined petroleum follows, with the U.S. as a sole leader in both exports and imports. The list also includes goods such as pharmaceuticals, gold, crude petroleum, telephone, broadcasting equipment, diamonds, petroleum gas, and aircrafts [20].

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Authors in [23] proposed a machine learning model for predicting agricultural commodity prices over one-, two-, and three-month periods ahead. They used the multivariate relevance vector machine based on Bayesian learning for regression and compared the performance of the MVRVM model to that of multiple-output artificial neural networks. Authors in [24] applied data mining to detect relationship patterns in customs administration data with market prices and current exchange rates in Ethiopia and discovered association rules to generate note worthy import/export patterns. They used datasets from the Ethiopian Revenue and Customs Authority, Central Statistics Agency, and the National Bank of Ethiopia and applied the WEKA tool for data analysis purposes, and the results verified that imported textile was significantly related to the market price and the currency exchange rate. They also concluded the Apriori algorithm as the fastest one in discovering association rules. Authors in [25] predicted bilateral trade flow, an important economic indicator, by using the gravity model of trade with a fully connected feed-forward neural network. They experimented with machine learning models by varying hidden layers and neurons in each hidden layer and found that fully connected feed-forward neural networks can improve the gravity model's prediction performance. They also proposed that the LSTM model may yield better results than fully connected neural networks for time series data. Author in [26] used machine learning and data mining techniques for publicly available commodity data and forecasted country GDP, finding a correlation between export-import data and GDP. He considered commodity trade and GDP as inputs to the algorithm and designed a model to predict GDP for another day with the given commodity trade for the new day. He used a multi-class support vector machine with a genetic algorithm based on a fuzzy set and artificial neural network to predict GDP. Authors in [27] implemented a back-propagation neural network based on a genetic algorithm for port throughput forecasting. They used a 12-year dataset such that 11 years of data was used for simulations/training and the final year was used for forecasting. They verified the proposed hybrid model, the GA-BP forecasting model, to show better accuracy but it took longer to converge.

Authors in [28] proposed a new machine learning approach for price modeling using a neural network with an advanced signal-processing tool. They used the proposed model to forecast prices of commodities such as coal, crude oil, and electricity and employed a mixture of a Gaussian neural network, showing significant improvements relative to other popular models. Authors in [29] constructed a GARCH model using an artificial neural network and evaluated its ability to forecast stock market volatility. They compared the

performance of their model to that of other popular volatility models for various international stock indices. Authors in [30] proposed a model to predict future gold rates based on 22 market variables using machine learning techniques. They collected data from various online sources and implemented a linear regression model using artificial neural networks with the rapid miner tool. Authors in [31] proposed a unified modeling framework to justify the empirical regularity in the international trade network and analyzed the international trade network each year with exports of the country with other countries. They constructed a basic model with a directed weighted network for unified modeling.

IV. MACHINE LEARNING IN GLOBAL TRADE DATA

Machine learning applies artificial intelligence (AI) to automatically learn and improve from experience without being specifically programmed. Machine learning focuses on the development of computer programs for accessing and learning from data. The process of learning begins with observations or data, including examples, direct experience, and instructions, to identify certain patterns in data for making better decisions. The main aim is to allow the computer to learn automatically without human intervention and engage in appropriate actions. AI and machine learning represent a good way for financial institutions to optimize margin valuation adjustment (MVA), which can be performed through the assistance of machine learning by reducing margins for derivatives through a combination of “executing pairs of offsetting derivative trades” and “executing offsetting strategies with the same dealer” [21]. By choosing the best combination of the initial margin, machine learning reduces trades in a given period of time, and the basis for this is the degree of initial margin reduction in the past from various combinations of trades [20]. Financial institutions emphasize cost-effective means for regulatory requirements, such as efficient trade execution, data reporting, and prudent regulation. In this regard, AI can be used to obtain information and process orders, and machine learning can help

create “trading robots” that can respond quickly to market changes. Therefore, such innovations can be used by firms to estimate financial impacts more accurately and minimize trading costs [20].

V. METHODOLOGY

A. Datasets

The data for this research study is gathered from [32]. The data consisted of yearly import/export data from 217 countries for the 1960-2017 period. Data were collected from the BoP (Balance of Payments) statistics yearbook and presented in USD. Several missing data points were identified as a result of no substantial import/export participation by some countries during early years. Therefore, the data for the last 43 years were considered in this study (i.e., 1975-2017). The data containing the top 10 countries in imports and exports were extracted from the primary data source for the analysis. The data (in billion USD) were used for further analysis. Tables I and II present the import and export data, respectively, for the study period. Datasets show the U.S. as leading both imports and exports from 1975 to 2017. Therefore, it is evident that the U.S. had the highest GDP and the GDP was growing at a constant pace. For better understanding, the import and export datasets are plotted in Figures 1 and 2 respectively.

Fig. 1. Increase in imports.

TABLE I. IMPORTS (IN BILLON \$) FOR 1975-2017

Year	Canada	Colombia	Germany	UK	Israel	India	Netherlands	Sweden	US	S. Africa
1975	42	3	94	64	7	7	40	21	120	12
1976	47	3	108	66	7	6	44	23	149	11
1977	49	3	123	74	8	7	51	24	180	10
1978	53	4	149	88	9	9	60	25	208	12
1979	63	4	193	115	11	12	76	35	248	15
1980	71	6	222	134	12	17	88	40	291	23
1981	79	7	195	122	13	18	76	36	310	26
1982	67	7	186	119	12	18	72	34	299	21
1983	74	6	181	118	12	18	70	32	323	18
1984	88	6	178	123	12	18	70	33	399	19
1985	93	6	184	128	12	19	73	35	410	13
1986	99	6	226	148	13	20	86	41	449	15
1987	107	6	271	183	17	23	104	51	501	18
1988	128	7	298	222	18	26	114	58	546	21
1989	141	7	319	233	18	29	119	62	580	21
1990	148	7	412	264	21	30	142	71	616	22
1991	152	7	452	251	23	28	146	66	610	22
1992	157	9	485	267	24	30	157	68	656	23
1993	168	12	420	255	27	31	144	56	713	24
1994	183	14	464	284	31	38	159	66	802	27
1995	199	16	559	327	36	49	210	81	891	34
1996	209	17	553	355	38	55	211	85	956	34

Year	Canada	Colombia	Germany	UK	Israel	India	Netherlands	Sweden	US	S. Africa
1997	237	19	537	380	38	59	206	85	1040	35
1998	241	18	565	396	36	60	217	90	1100	33
1999	259	14	579	419	41	63	223	91	1230	31
2000	287	15	595	440	47	74	231	97	1450	34
2001	268	17	587	439	44	72	231	87	1370	32
2002	271	16	589	471	43	76	243	91	1400	33
2003	295	17	726	529	45	93	286	113	1510	44
2004	337	21	858	625	53	131	363	134	1770	59
2005	385	26	934	686	59	182	392	149	2000	69
2006	430	31	1080	784	63	225	441	169	2220	84
2007	471	38	1250	841	75	279	522	204	2360	98
2008	508	46	1410	867	85	379	595	226	2550	108
2009	412	40	1130	677	64	328	486	167	1970	83
2010	500	49	1270	753	77	439	532	197	2350	103
2011	568	64	1500	840	93	553	615	233	2680	123
2012	587	70	1410	844	93	580	600	221	2760	124
2013	586	71	1480	869	92	560	618	224	2760	122
2014	585	76	1510	915	95	554	632	231	2870	116
2015	531	65	1310	840	85	492	552	200	2760	100
2016	513	55	1330	804	90	472	555	202	2710	90
2017	548	57	1460	838	97	561	619	222	2900	100

TABLE II. EXPORTS (IN BILLON \$) FOR 1975-2017

Year	Canada	Colombia	Germany	UK	Israel	India	Netherlands	Sweden	US	S. Africa
1975	39	3	103	60	4	6	43	21	130	11
1976	45	3	119	63	5	7	47	22	142	10
1977	48	4	137	76	6	8	52	23	152	12
1978	54	4	166	92	7	9	60	27	178	15
1979	64	5	198	117	8	10	75	34	223	20
1980	75	6	217	146	9	12	87	39	272	29
1981	81	5	200	136	9	12	81	36	294	24
1982	80	5	201	128	9	13	78	34	275	21
1983	86	4	192	121	9	14	75	34	266	21
1984	100	6	193	122	10	14	76	36	291	20
1985	101	5	207	132	10	13	79	37	289	19
1986	102	7	272	144	12	14	92	44	310	20
1987	112	7	326	175	14	16	109	53	349	26
1988	132	7	358	191	15	18	122	60	431	27
1989	142	8	379	199	16	21	128	63	487	26
1990	149	9	457	239	18	23	153	71	535	28
1991	149	10	443	240	17	24	157	70	578	27
1992	155	10	473	254	20	25	169	72	617	28
1993	168	10	421	246	21	28	160	62	643	30
1994	189	11	468	277	24	32	178	74	703	31
1995	218	13	571	322	28	39	235	96	794	35
1996	233	14	573	352	30	41	236	101	852	36
1997	249	15	563	383	32	45	231	101	934	37
1998	253	14	594	384	33	46	240	105	933	35
1999	283	14	594	393	38	52	242	106	970	34
2000	328	16	601	409	47	60	247	112	1080	37
2001	310	16	622	401	41	63	248	105	1010	36
2002	304	15	680	421	40	71	260	107	979	37
2003	329	16	819	480	44	85	322	131	1020	48
2004	382	20	1000	563	54	116	410	161	1160	59
2005	431	25	1080	622	59	155	446	174	1290	69
2006	465	29	1240	719	63	193	499	199	1460	80
2007	502	35	1480	765	73	240	593	235	1650	94
2008	536	44	1640	781	84	305	673	257	1840	103
2009	392	39	1300	625	70	261	550	188	1580	84
2010	469	46	1440	689	82	348	603	220	1850	108
2011	547	64	1690	799	95	446	692	262	2130	127
2012	551	69	1630	792	93	444	679	249	2220	118
2013	556	68	1710	813	98	468	711	253	2290	113
2014	568	65	1780	854	100	486	727	257	2380	110
2015	492	46	1580	790	94	429	632	225	2260	97
2016	476	42	1600	749	97	430	641	225	2210	92
2017	511	48	1740	802	102	488	714	240	2330	104

Fig. 2. Increase in exports.

With the growth in imports and exports of all countries identified, as shown in these plots, data analysis was conducted using linear regression to identify the correlation coefficient and other performance measures.

B. Data Analysis

The GDP of any country is dependent on import and export data since these factors make the greatest contributions to the country’s economy, and several algorithms have been implemented for the analysis of trade data. Therefore, this study focused on analyzing import and export data. The study initially employed linear regression, followed by a comparison with other machine learning algorithms. Here, preprocessed data from 10 countries were used as the input for linear regression, and the results for export and import datasets were obtained as shown in Tables III and IV, respectively.

TABLE III. EXPORTS ANALYSIS FOR TOP 10 COUNTRIES

Country	CC	MAE	RMSE	RAE (%)	RRS(%)
Canada	0.9642	40.606	46.7947	25.1067	25.8104
Colombia	0.8346	8.3626	10.8224	49.9367	53.1576
Germany	0.9375	162.9892	195.2004	32.1998	33.721
India	0.8353	78.3047	90.7998	54.2975	53.1019
Israel	0.9484	9.2247	10.3887	31.6044	30.7659
Netherlands	0.933	72.6982	84.1967	34.3541	34.8714
S. Africa	0.8842	13.7084	16.464	43.1783	45.1946
Sweden	0.942	22.7929	27.3736	31.1841	32.5885
UK	0.9639	61.4828	70.191	25.9338	25.899
US	0.9566	184.4345	211.1925	29.5354	28.3296

CC: Correlation Coefficient, MAE: Mean Absolute Error, RMSE: Root Mean Square Error, RAE: Relative Absolute Error, RRS: Root Relative Squared Error

TABLE IV. IMPORTS ANALYSIS FOR TOP 10 COUNTRIES

Country	CC	MAE	RMSE	RAE (%)	RRS(%)
Canada	0.9585	44.3818	51.9594	27.3267	27.6743
Colombia	0.8578	9.0713	11.2877	48.4398	49.8184
Germany	0.9447	130.7667	154.7405	31.125	31.8091
India	0.8272	94.3616	110.4496	54.8779	54.241
Israel	0.9562	7.6478	8.748	29.0447	28.426
Netherlands	0.9347	62.5513	71.9923	34.2352	34.4388
South Africa	0.8703	15.8974	18.4622	46.8866	47.7568
Sweden	0.9344	20.9784	25.3766	32.8641	34.5429
UK	0.9628	67.9066	77.7684	25.9899	26.2868
US	0.9639	221.3444	249.555	25.9518	25.8817

CC: Correlation Coefficient, MAE: Mean Absolute Error, RMSE: Root Mean Square Error, RAE: Relative Absolute Error, RRS: Root Relative Squared Error

From these import and export Tables, it can be observed that the correlation coefficient is close to 1, indicating a strong

positive linear relationship. However, the RMSE is slightly high in some cases. Since the dataset consisted of only 43 instances (last 43 years of data), the linear regression model showed good correlations and high RMSE values. Therefore, further analysis using other machine learning algorithms was conducted with import and export datasets from the U.S. and Germany.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To investigate on the best-performing machine learning algorithms for a better analysis of trade data and to forecast country GDP, this study considered 5 machine learning algorithms:

- Linear Regression (LR)
- RBF Regressor (RBF)
- Support Vector Machine (SVM)
- Regression by Discretization (RD)
- Reduced Error Pruning Tree(REP)

The U.S. and Germany import and export datasets were used as input datasets. A 10-fold cross-validation method was implemented to select training and testing datasets. Here correlation coefficients, root mean squared error, relative absolute error, and root relative squared error were considered as performance measures. A two-tailed test with a 0.05 confidence level was conducted and the results for these four performance measures are respectively shown in Tables V-VIII. Table V shows the correlation coefficients obtained for 4 datasets in the experiment with 5 algorithms. The Table shows that the RBF algorithm generated better models with high correlation coefficients, followed by RD, LR, SVM, and REP. Table VI (relative absolute error analysis) shows that RBF generated models with much smaller errors than LR and SVM. The results for RD lie between RBF and REP results. Therefore, RBF can be considered to perform well with respect to the relative absolute error measure.

TABLE V. CORRELATION COEFFICIENT ANALYSIS

Data Set	LR	RBF	SVM	RD	REP
Germany_exports	0.97	0.99	0.97	0.97	0.96
Germany_imports	0.97	0.99	0.97	0.97	0.96
US_exports	0.98	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.97
US_imports	0.98	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.97

TABLE VI. RELATIVE ABSOLUTE ERROR ANALYSIS

Data Set	LR	RBF	SVM	RD	REP
Germany_exports	35.46	13.78	35.85	20.99	22.45
Germany_imports	34.41	15.57	32.05	21.36	23.81
US_exports	34.21	12.02	33.16	16.60	22.30
US_imports	29.38	9.58	30.72	16.36	20.82

TABLE VII. ROOT MEAN SQUARED ERROR ANALYSIS

Data Set	LR	RBF	SVM	RD	REP
Germany_exports	187.53	86.55	195.54	118.76	139.53
Germany_imports	146.63	78.10	149.10	105.87	119.36
US_exports	205.34	83.24	237.78	111.97	155.62
US_imports	247.66	106.71	262.79	156.85	202.58

TABLE VIII. ROOT RELATIVE SQUARED ERROR ANALYSIS

Data Set	LR	RBF	SVM	RD	REP
Germany exports	36.13	15.43	36.88	22.80	26.56
Germany imports	33.85	16.69	33.01	23.69	26.95
US exports	30.89	12.26	33.36	16.81	23.58
US imports	28.26	11.45	29.47	17.66	23.25

Table VII (root mean squared error) and Table VIII (root relative squared error) also verify RBF as providing better results than the other algorithms. Although RMS values are high (with a smaller dataset), RBF obtains 60% better results than LR.

The performance plots for the above measures using the RBF algorithm are shown in Figures 3-6.

Fig. 3. Correlation coefficient.

Fig. 4. Mean absolute error.

Fig. 5. Root mean squared error

Given these measures, the RBF algorithm is shown to provide good performance with a gain of about 60%. The

results demonstrate that RBF outperformed the other four algorithms and that the models generated using RBF produced better results in forecasting of country GDP.

Fig. 6. Root relative squared error

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Trade analysis results show a strong positive linear relationship in trade statistics. Imports and exports increased linearly with the world engaging in increased trade activity. In particular, the U.S., China, Japan, and India have made remarkable progress in the past decade in both exports and imports. This study takes two different directions. The first direction is the analysis of the top 10 import/export countries to show the correlation in trade data, and the second is to investigate different machine learning algorithms to identify the best algorithm for the prediction of trade data and country GDP. Here the WEKA data analysis tool was used for data analysis, and the experiments were conducted using five machine learning algorithms. The results show that all five algorithms exhibited good correlations but that the RBF algorithm outperformed the other algorithms. This suggests that the RBF algorithm may perform well in forecasting trade data to predict a country's GDP.

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